

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Farmers' intention to improve soil quality: a case study from Flanders

In Flanders, a survey has been conducted to understand farmers' intention to invest in soil quality. We received 131 completed surveys, of which 37 responses from organic farmers. We asked farmers to indicate from a list of 17 indicators which they used to evaluate their soil quality. On average, 7 of these indicators were used by each farmer. The most commonly used were soil structure (68%), pH (77%) and organic matter content (79%), followed by ease of cultivation (61%) and crop yield (68%). We do observe differences between organic and non-organic farmers. Organic farmers evaluated soil quality more often by looking at soil structure (87% versus 61%), water-holding capacity (58% versus 34%) and the number of earthworm corridors (61% versus 16%), while conventional farmers rely more often on soil pH (61% versus 83%) and nitrogen content (21% versus 47%). Based on these indicators, 2 thirds of farmers indicate that they

consider the quality of their soil to be reasonably good to very good. One-third indicate that the quality is neither good nor bad, or they do not know. Almost all farmers (96%) indicate that improving soil quality on their farm is very important. However, when we ask about potential practices and their contribution to improving soil quality, we observe differences between organic and non-organic farmers. More than 60% of all farmers think crop residue incorporation (65%), wide crop rotation (63%) and cover crops (62%) contribute strongly to soil quality. Conventional farmers are more convinced of the contribution of precision fertilisation (34% vs 16%). More than half of organic farmers are convinced of the positive contribution of reduced tillage (non-inversion tillage, reduced depth, direct sowing), compared to <20% among conventional farmers.

1. Yellow mustard as cover crop.

KEYWORDS

Survey, farmers perception, soil quality

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